

INCLUSIVE EDUCATION AND INNOVATION: ERASMUS+ CONTRIBUTIONS AND THEIR IMPACT ON THE EDUCATION COMMUNITY

Educación inclusiva e innovación: aportaciones de Erasmus+ y su impacto en la comunidad educativa

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Abstract

Inclusive education and pedagogical innovation are fundamental pillars for building more equitable and cohesive societies. Aware of this challenge, various Erasmus+ projects have launched initiatives to address diversity and improve educational practices across Europe. Through a systematic review of 31 projects identified as good practices in inclusion, approaches combining active methodologies, digital technologies, and socio-emotional intervention strategies were analysed. The methodology involved classifying projects according to their main focus (direct educational inclusion, social inclusion, inclusive technology, or mixed approaches), identifying the tangible outcomes produced, and assessing their transferability potential. The results show a high production of open educational resources, such as practical manuals, learning platforms, gamified activities, teacher training programs, peer mediation guides, and digital literacy materials, among others. These resources, mostly multilingual and openly accessible, offer replicable models that strengthen teachers' competencies, enrich learning environments, and promote educational equity. Furthermore, the integration of inclusive methodologies, the use of accessible technologies, and the promotion of socio-emotional skills contribute to improving pedagogical quality in schools. The systematization and dissemination of these good practices reinforce the idea that Erasmus+ projects not only foster innovation but also leave a sustainable legacy to transform teaching, promote the participation of vulnerable groups, and build a more inclusive and resilient European educational community.

Key words: inclusive education; educational innovation; educational best practices; Technology Integration; Erasmus+

Resumen

La educación inclusiva y la innovación pedagógica son pilares fundamentales para construir sociedades más equitativas y cohesionadas. Conscientes de este desafío, diversos proyectos Erasmus+ han impulsado iniciativas para atender a la diversidad y mejorar las prácticas educativas en Europa. A través de una revisión sistemática de 31 proyectos seleccionados como buenas prácticas en inclusión, se analizaron enfoques que combinan metodologías activas, tecnologías digitales y estrategias de intervención socioemocional. La metodología consistió en clasificar los proyectos según su principal

ámbito de acción (inclusión educativa directa, inclusión social, tecnología inclusiva o proyectos mixtos), identificar los productos tangibles generados y valorar su potencial de transferibilidad. Los resultados muestran una alta producción de recursos educativos abiertos, tales como manuales prácticos, plataformas de aprendizaje, actividades gamificadas, programas de formación docente, guías para la mediación escolar y contenidos de alfabetización digital, entre otros. Estos recursos, en su mayoría multilingües y de acceso libre, ofrecen modelos replicables que fortalecen las competencias del profesorado y enriquecen los entornos de aprendizaje, aunque su aplicación generalizada sigue enfrentando retos como la brecha digital o la escasez de personal especializado en algunos contextos. Además, la integración de metodologías inclusivas, el uso de tecnologías accesibles y el fomento de competencias socioemocionales contribuyen a mejorar la calidad pedagógica en los centros educativos. La sistematización y difusión de estas buenas prácticas refuerza la idea de que los proyectos Erasmus+ no solo innovan, sino que dejan un legado que puede orientar políticas públicas más eficaces, impulsar la participación de colectivos vulnerables y construir una comunidad educativa europea más inclusiva y resiliente.

Palabras clave: educación inclusiva; innovación educativa; buenas prácticas educativas; integración tecnológica; Erasmus+.

1. Introduction

Educational inclusion has been consolidated as one of the fundamental pillars in international education agendas, driven by the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (UNESCO, 2017) and the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, 2008). The promotion of quality, equitable and inclusive education for all is an urgent and cross-cutting challenge that affects all levels of the education system.

Despite regulatory advances, recent reports such as the International Study of Teaching and Learning (TALIS, *Teaching and Learning International Survey*) of the OECD (OECD, 2019, 2020) and the Global Education Monitoring Report (GEM), *Global Education Monitoring Report*) of UNESCO (UNESCO, 2024) reveal that important structural and cultural challenges remain. Education systems must face the lack of human and material resources, the need for more specialized and continuous teacher training in inclusive strategies, and the difficulty of adequately accompanying schools in their adaptation to the needs of all students.

In daily practice, schools are often overwhelmed by the complexity of the situations they have to deal with. The shortage of specialised personnel, such as therapeutic pedagogy, hearing and language professionals or educational technicians, limits the ability to

respond to the multiple needs of students. Added to this is the growing diversity in the classroom, which covers not only cultural or linguistic aspects, but also profiles with disabilities, developmental disorders, learning difficulties or complex socio-emotional situations. All of this requires planning and personalization that is not always possible, especially in contexts with high ratios and limited resources.

In addition, many teachers express feeling overwhelmed by the number and variety of needs they must address in their classroom without sufficient training or specialized support. Although there is a growing awareness of the importance of inclusion, the necessary tools to apply truly inclusive methodologies are not always available. The pressure of the curriculum, the administrative burden and the lack of time for coordination between professionals also make it difficult to provide adequate care.

Another key, and often invisible, aspect is the difficulties in establishing a fluid and constructive relationship with families. In many cases, families struggle to accept the diagnosis or understand the extent of their children's struggles. This can generate tensions about the expectations they have regarding the educational center. Sometimes it is not easy to explain how far an ordinary school with support can go, and when it may be more appropriate to consider other options, such as a special education center. Achieving open, empathetic and realistic communication requires time, accompaniment and joint involvement that is not always easy to achieve.

In this context, it is crucial to consider inclusion not only as a matter of physical access to education, but also as a process of profound transformation of school cultures, pedagogical practices and educational policies. Technology, methodological innovation and international cooperation emerge as key allies to advance in this transformation.

The role of schools, teachers and education inspectorates becomes essential in this process. They must not only lead and accompany the implementation of inclusive strategies, but also act as agents of change that promote a broader and more transformative vision of education. The education inspectorate, in particular, plays a decisive role in ensuring that inclusive policies are implemented effectively, in advising schools and in supporting teacher training and awareness-raising.

In the Spanish context, attention to inclusion has been reinforced through the amendment of the Ley Orgánica on Education (LOE) (Ley Orgánica 2/2006, 2006) through Ley Orgánica 3/2020 (LOMLOE) (Ley Orgánica 3/2020, 2020). This reform consolidates the principle of educational inclusion as an essential element of quality and equity in the

system, and expressly introduces Universal Design for Learning (UDL) (Alba Pastor, 2019) as a pedagogical strategy to attend to the diversity of the student body. The LOMLOE is committed to a preventive and proactive approach, which prioritises the early detection of needs and the deployment of support in ordinary environments, reinforcing the responsibility of schools and promoting teacher training in inclusive methodologies.

The LOMLOE not only reinforces inclusion as an essential educational principle, but also makes explicit the need to guarantee equal opportunities through specific actions: early detection of needs, specialised personnel, and methodological adaptation based on principles of equity, standardisation and inclusion. This orientation is reflected in article 2.bis of the LOE, which establishes that the education system must be governed by quality, equity and non-discrimination, guaranteeing that students with SEN have access to quality education under conditions of equality.

The connection of the Spanish framework with the Incheon Declaration and SDG 4 (UNESCO, 2016) it is strengthened by understanding inclusion as part of the universal right to education. UNESCO, OECD, EU (Council of the European Union. General Secretariat of the Council, 2010; OECD, 2021; UNESCO, 2020) They point out that no educational objective should be considered achieved as long as there is only one excluded student. Hence the need to implement proactive policies that favour equity and inclusion, a premise also present in the design of many Erasmus+ projects analysed.

This article analyses the main trends and challenges in educational inclusion in Europe, explores the contributions of Erasmus+ projects that have been catalogued as good practices in this field, and reflects on the indispensable role played by schools, teachers and education inspectorates in building truly inclusive classrooms.

2. Literature review

The European Union, through initiatives such as the Erasmus+ programme (European Commission, 2024) and the European Strategy on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities 2021-2030 (A Union of Equality: Strategy on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities 2021-2030, 2021), has placed inclusion as a guiding principle of its educational policies. These strategic frameworks seek to ensure that all students, regardless of their personal characteristics or circumstances, have access to quality education in conditions of equity and full accessibility.

International reports, in particular OECD TALIS (OECD, 2019, 2020) and UNESCO GEM (UNESCO, 2020, 2024), provide key recommendations for more inclusive education systems. TALIS highlights the urgent need to strengthen initial and continuing teacher training in inclusive methodologies and the use of adaptive technologies, as well as underlining the importance of fostering professional learning communities that allow for the exchange of good practices. For its part, the GEM Report recommends integrating specific inclusion indicators into national and international educational assessments and highlights the transformative potential of digital technologies to close educational equity gaps.

However, taking these recommendations to the field is complex. Many schools, especially in rural contexts or with a high concentration of vulnerable students, do not have sufficient specialized staff to adequately address the diversity of the classroom. This implies that generalist teachers take on tasks for which they often do not feel sufficiently trained or accompanied. Although there is a growing training offer in inclusion, access to it is not always feasible due to time limitations, lack of coverage of substitutions or lack of continuity in the programs. This lack of human resources and specific training generates a sense of overflow and frustration among teachers, especially when they have to deal simultaneously with very diverse situations – from developmental disorders or learning difficulties to complex social realities – without stable support. Not surprisingly, the data reflect a considerable gap in teacher training: only 35% of European teachers have received specific training in inclusion (OECD, 2019).

2.1. Educational technology as an aid to inclusion

To address this situation, it is crucial not only to strengthen human resources, but also to bet on tools that contribute to making attention to diversity more viable. Inclusive educational technology is presented here as an ally to alleviate part of the teaching overload, personalize learning and facilitate attention more adjusted to each profile. To this end, it is essential to design strategies that enhance the technological training of teachers and the strengthening of collaborative professional networks. Training workshops on inclusive technologies, focused on the practical use of tools such as Artificial Intelligence (AI), Augmented Reality (AR) and Virtual Reality (VR), as well as the creation of digital platforms that facilitate the exchange of resources and experiences, emerge as key proposals to move towards a more inclusive education.

The incorporation of emerging technologies is revolutionizing the educational landscape, offering new opportunities to personalize learning and remove barriers to access through technologies such as smart screen readers or sign language translation assistants. According to the UNESCO report (2023), AI has enormous potential to address inequalities and improve educational inclusion, dynamically adapting learning content to individual needs. Tools such as smart screen readers or automatic sign language translation assistants help reduce barriers without requiring permanent intervention by the teacher. . Likewise, the Educause Review report (2024) highlights how AI tools are advancing accessibility for students with disabilities, allowing for more equitable learning experiences (Jenay, 2024).

On the one hand, AR provides immersive environments that enrich traditional teaching materials, integrating information in a visual and accessible way (Mendoza Melazco *et al.*, 2022; Rivadulla López & Rodríguez Correa, 2020). This facilitates the understanding of abstract concepts, particularly for students with special educational needs, improving their motivation and knowledge retention (Mirza *et al.*, 2025).

On the other hand, VR demonstrates its ability to create realistic simulations that allow students to experience complex situations and allow them to be an active part and interact in a real-life environment (X. P. Lin *et al.*, 2024; Ortega Rodríguez, 2022; Radianti *et al.*, 2020). The use of VR not only favors the understanding of content, but also awareness of functional diversity, promoting empathy and inclusive attitudes (Córcoles-Charcos *et al.*, 2023).

Both AR and VR significantly improve students' engagement and motivation towards the teaching process, while promoting the inclusion of students with learning difficulties (Rodríguez Cano *et al.*, 2021; Valero Franco & Berns, 2023)

In addition, the *Big Data* is transforming educational assessment through personalised monitoring of student progress (Baig *et al.*, 2020; L. Lin *et al.*, 2024). Big Data-assisted learning ecosystems promote more inclusive and adaptive educational environments, favoring the universal design of resources from their conception (JosephNg *et al.*, 2025; Mella-Norambuena *et al.*, 2023). In this way, more accurate learning profiles can be generated, patterns of progress can be identified and pedagogical strategies can be adjusted in a more agile way, helping to prioritize efforts in contexts where resources are limited.

In addition to all of the above, collaborative digital platforms, both between teachers and families, can contribute to improving coordination and sharing validated resources, generating a support network that does not depend exclusively on the physical presence of specialists in the school.

Together, these technological and methodological strategies shape a more inclusive, adaptive and resilient educational ecosystem, aligned with the principles of equity, inclusion, quality and accessibility that guide contemporary education policies in Europe.

2.2. Erasmus+ as a catalyst for inclusion

The Erasmus+ programme, launched in 2014 and renewed for the period 2021-2027, has become a key tool to drive the transformation of European education systems towards more inclusive, equitable and innovative models. With a clear focus on inclusion, the programme allocates specific resources to encourage the participation of students with disabilities, from disadvantaged backgrounds and from traditionally underrepresented groups (European Commission, 2022, 2024). In addition, Erasmus+ actively promotes the use of innovative methodologies, educational digitalisation and transnational cooperation to develop good practices that can be transferred and scaled up to other contexts.

Erasmus+ integrates inclusion as a cross-cutting priority in all its projects, from student mobility to cooperation partnerships. According to the European Education and Culture Executive Agency (European Commission, 2014, 2023), inclusion actions aim to remove barriers to access, adapting activities and providing additional support to those in need. The programme's connection to the Sustainable Development Goals, especially SDG 4 (Quality Education) (UNESCO, 2021) and SDG 10 (Reduced inequalities) (UNESCO, 2017), reinforces its commitment to education that is truly accessible to all.

Several Erasmus+ projects have been recognised as good practices in educational inclusion. For example, the "IncludEd" project (University of Trento *et al.*, 2025) focuses on creating accessible educational materials through collaboration between students, teachers, and technology experts, promoting UDL (Alba Pastor, 2019). Another example is "SignHub" (Pompeu Fabra University, 2020) a platform that combines AI and AR to facilitate the learning of sign language in multilingual contexts, responding to the need for linguistic accessibility in classrooms (Laborda *et al.*, 2024; Valero Franco & Berns, 2023).

Erasmus+ has also served as a platform for the development and implementation of emerging technologies in the field of education. AI has been used in projects that create virtual assistants for people who are deaf or visually impaired (OECD, 2024; UNESCO, 2023, 2024). AR has made it possible to overlay visual information on science and math lessons, making it easier for students with special educational needs to understand abstract concepts (Mirza *et al.*, 2025).

Various experiences show that the use of accessible digital resources, VR simulations and AR applications is a key strategy to promote the participation of students with functional diversity and the development of skills in an immersive way (Fonseca *et al.*, 2021; OECD, 2022). A prominent example is the "VR4VIP" project (Berufsförderungswerk Düring GmbH *et al.*, 2023), which investigates the application of VR for the visually impaired, demonstrating that these technologies, when implemented under an inclusive pedagogical approach, significantly improve accessibility and student engagement. Likewise, the project "PRO. D.I.G.Y" (Social Academy of Sciences *et al.*, 2024) underscores the value of integrating VR and AR solutions to prepare people with disabilities in emergency situations, strengthening their autonomy and safety in work and educational settings.

Likewise, projects such as "DigiEdu4All" Association for Development Policy and Global Justice *et al.*, 2023) They have developed digital tools that allow them to create inclusive learning environments, supported by accessible applications and adapted multimedia resources. These initiatives not only improve the educational opportunities of students with disabilities, but also benefit the entire educational community by promoting more flexible and personalized methodologies.

On the other hand, the use of Big Data in Erasmus+ educational projects, such as "Big Data in Psychological Assessment" has made it possible to identify learning patterns, detect early support needs and design inclusive strategies based on evidence (L. Linen *et al.*, 2024; Universität des Saarlandes *et al.*, 2020).

Another fundamental axis of this type of project is the training of teachers. Erasmus+ promotes workshops, training courses and exchange networks that allow teachers to acquire skills in inclusive technology and adaptive methodologies. These programs promote collaborative learning, universal design, and pedagogical innovation in the classroom. There is also explicit recognition with the European Prize for Innovative Teaching (in English *European Innovative Teaching Award*) that allows us to identify

good practices of the teaching staff (European Commission. Directorate General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture., 2023).

Programs such as *Novice Educator Support and Training* (NEST, (for its acronym in English) (Teach for Bulgaria *et al.*, 2023) They offer practical training and continuous support to novice teachers, especially in schools with high cultural and social diversity, promoting the use of inclusive methodologies and strengthening professional collaboration networks. Teachers who participate in these programs report a significant improvement in their competencies to manage diverse classrooms and apply personalized approaches that serve all students (European Commission, 2020, 2021).

In addition, the collaborative platforms set up under Erasmus+ encourage the exchange of good practices, the development of inclusive learning materials and the establishment of professional networks that last beyond the duration of the projects.

Finally, it is worth mentioning that many schools have managed to transform their inclusive practices thanks to participation in Erasmus+ projects, incorporating adaptive technologies, making methodologies more flexible and strengthening collaboration between teachers and families

3. Method

Systematic knowledge and the dissemination of these good practices are essential to transform current educational models and move towards a more equitable and higher quality school, where each student can fully develop their potential. In order to illustrate concrete examples of good practices in educational inclusion, a systematic search has been carried out on the Erasmus+ Project Results Platform (PRPE+) (European Commission, 2025), where projects have been selected based on the following selection criteria:

- Project completed.
- With results.
- Explicit recognition as good practice.
- Etiquetado como “European Innovative Teaching Award”.
- Temáticas de las categorías: “Access for disadvantaged”, “Inclusion, promoting equality and non-discrimination”, “Integration of refugees”, “Disabilities - special needs”, “Inclusion – equity”.

The interest in using these selection criteria is to locate the projects that have been considered successful, not only because of the project itself, but also because a good practice of teaching innovation has been demonstrated, have results that can be transferred to other institutions or educational centers and the categories are linked to inclusion.

The analysis was structured on the basis of the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA) framework (Page, McKenzie, *et al.*, 2021; Page, Moher, *et al.*, 2021), usually applied in systematic reviews, adapting it to the study of educational innovation projects. Likewise, elements of the *Systematic Research Projects Reviews* (SRPR) approach were incorporated, which offers a procedure for reviewing databases of projects on specific topics (García-Holgado *et al.*, 2020; Alonso de Castro, 2023).

3.1. Procedure

The process was organised in five stages (Figure 1), designed to ensure a systematic and reproducible analysis of Erasmus+ projects linked to educational inclusion. This sequence allows for a broad initial identification and, at the same time, an in-depth thematic analysis, adapted to the diversity of formats, recipients and levels of documentation.

Figure 1.

Key stages of the Erasmus+ project analysis methodology.

Source: Own elaboration

Each step of the process is described below:

1. Identification of projects. In April 2025, a search was carried out using the PRPE+, selecting the projects with the topics indicated above. In this process, more than 34,500 projects were connected to these themes.

2. Eligibility selection. Based on the themes chosen and related to inclusion, the projects that were labelled as "Good Practice" and "European Innovative Teaching Award" were identified. In this phase, the group of projects was reduced to 50.

3. Inclusion criteria. To refine the dataset, only those completed projects that offered publicly accessible outcomes (e.g., platforms, training materials, reports) were

considered. Only 31 projects out of the 50 that passed the preliminary phase met this inclusion criterion.

4. Thematic analysis. A qualitative analysis was carried out reviewing the descriptions, documentation and public results of the projects, identifying the most outstanding aspects of them to improve inclusion in the classrooms.

5. Synthesis and interpretation. The aim has been to identify what actions are being carried out in the field of inclusion at the European level, outstanding tools and aspects that are detected as deficient and could be improved.

4. Results

In total, 31 projects have been located (Alonso de Castro, 2025) that meet the criteria indicated and are shown in Table 1. This figure remains the same at the current time, August 2025.

Table 1.

List of projects

Reference	Summary
2021-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000032841	It strengthens socio-emotional competencies in teachers and vulnerable students after the pandemic, promoting inclusive learning and resilience.
2021-2-LV01-KA210-SCH-000049347	It promotes social inclusion and health through sports, plant nutrition and ecological activities in young people from various contexts.
2020-1-EL01-KA201-078810	It improves the educational and social inclusion of Roma students and families through teacher training and the creation of inclusive materials.
2020-1-DE03-KA229-077397	It promotes the social inclusion of students at risk of exclusion (due to linguistic, behavioural or mental barriers) through sports and physical activities adapted to all abilities.
2019-1-SK01-KA229-060793	Fostering social empathy, tolerance and respect in a multicultural school environment, equipping students with social, digital and communicative skills to build inclusive communities.
2019-1-NL01-KA201-060346	It promotes an inclusive view of health by challenging the perception that a healthy lifestyle is exclusive to people from affluent socioeconomic backgrounds.
2020-1-TR01-KA201-093698	It addresses the educational inclusion of students with medium intellectual disabilities (MID) through the integration of digital skills in the field of special education.
2019-1-EL01-KA229-062543	It has promoted social and educational inclusion through the introduction of peer-to-peer school mediation techniques. even during mobility restrictions due to the pandemic.
2020-1-LV01-KA201-077496	Integration of technologies and the STEAM (science, technology, engineering, art and mathematics) model in informal education environments. Technological learning was accessible, motivating and inclusive for students from

disadvantaged backgrounds

2018-1-NL01-KA201-038955	It focused on improving the educational and social inclusion of students with visual impairment and multiple disabilities (MDVI) through the use of assistive technologies.
2018-1-FI01-KA229-047288	Social inclusion from various perspectives adapted to the contexts of each partner, working with students from ethnic and linguistic minorities and groups at risk of exclusion.
2020-1-PL01-KA201-081490	She addressed the problem of bullying as a factor of social exclusion and early abandonment of education, working directly with students at risk, especially from vulnerable groups.
2019-1-BG01-KA201-062561	Address barriers to early childhood literacy, especially among ethnic minority students, migrants, refugees and children with special educational needs.
2017-1-BG01-KA201-036295	It addressed the need for early intervention in speech and language difficulties, key factors in academic success and social inclusion.
2018-1-FR01-KA229-048344	It promoted the inclusion of migrant students in European schools through innovative pedagogical practices focused on tolerance, solidarity and intercultural dialogue.
2017-1-SK01-KA201-035313	Based on project-based learning (PBL), teachers and students were trained in active methodologies focused on real problem solving and cooperation.
2017-1-FR01-KA219-037109	It promoted social and cultural inclusion in early childhood education through artistic and recreational activities that integrated all children, regardless of age, disability or social environment.
2017-1-EL01-KA219-036155	It addressed educational and social inclusion through the development of intercultural competences and raising awareness of human rights and the situation of refugees.
2017-1-LV01-KA219-035422	She integrated art, digital technologies and creativity as key tools to transform traditional education into a more inclusive, participatory and motivating model.
2018-1-CY01-KA229-046925	It promoted social cohesion, tolerance and educational inclusion through creative and participatory activities focused on combating discrimination, bullying and exclusion of refugees and asylum seekers.
2015-1-EL01-KA219-013904	It addressed the educational inclusion of students with special educational needs (SEN) through the integration of the arts (music, dance, theater, photography, cinema, poetry and crafts) as pedagogical and therapeutic tools.
2018-1-EL01-KA229-047808	Educational journey focused on cultural heritage, environmental awareness and European diversity.
2018-1-HR01-KA201-047499	It addressed the challenge of improving educational opportunities for learners from culturally and linguistically diverse backgrounds (DLLs) by focusing on literacy development through formal, non-formal and informal learning contexts.
2017-1-SE01-KA219-034589	It addresses learning barriers related to motivation, educational transitions and social exclusion. Based on active and student-centred methodologies
2016-1-CY01-KA201-017315	It focused on improving the reading motivation of students aged 9 to 15, especially those with low reading performance, through an innovative combination of personalized reading paths and digital creativity.
2017-1-HR01-KA219-035417	It focuses on the use of animal-assisted therapy as an innovative methodology to support students with special needs, learning difficulties, behavioral disorders, and hyperactivity.
2017-1-LT01-KA202-035218	Promotion of inclusive tourism, training professionals capable of advising SMEs in the tourism sector to improve their accessibility and quality of service for people with disabilities.
2017-1-IT02-KA201-	It brought together schools and associations from six

036699	European countries to promote the inclusion of students with disabilities, special educational needs (SEN), immigrants and disadvantaged students through music.
2018-1-BE02-KA101-046687	It focused on redesigning the playground as an accessible, safe and inclusive outdoor learning space for all students, including children with special educational needs.
2016-1-HR01-KA219-022165	He promoted equality, tolerance and human rights. Key topics such as gender, religion, origin, groups at risk of exclusion and linguistic diversity were addressed
2016-1-CZ01-KA219-023855	It addressed the educational inclusion of immigrant students, refugees, ethnic minorities (such as Roma and Somali students) and students with fewer opportunities.

Source: Own elaboration (European Commission, 2025)

The selected projects are connected to the principles of inclusion, diversity and/or educational equity; however, not all projects directly address educational inclusion in the strict sense, i.e., classroom adaptations, teacher training, or specific methodologies to address student diversity (Table 2). Approximately 18 projects focus on promoting direct educational inclusion, working from the school system itself and seeking to improve learning opportunities for all students. However, the rest of the initiatives, although they do not always intervene specifically in the classroom, contribute significantly to social and community inclusion, developing emotional, social or digital competences that favour cohesion, accessibility and equity, aspects that have an indirect, but significant, impact on educational environments.

Table 2.

Projects grouped by categories

Category	Projects
Direct educational inclusion (in the classroom, school adaptations, teacher training)	• 2021-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000032841 - Training #Emotional intelligent and #Acceptant #Mindsets for #Inclusion
	• 2019-1-NL01-KA201-060346 - Healthy Inclusive Lifestyle through Schools
	• 2020-1-TR01-KA201-093698 - INtegrating Special-needs Individuals into Digi-holistic Education
	• 2019-1-EL01-KA229-062543 - Cre@t1ve Conflict Resolution and Peer-to-Peer School Mediation
	• 2019-1-BG01-KA201-062561 - Learn and Play
	• 2017-1-BG01-KA201-036295 - Speech and Language Pathology Interactive Tools for Teachers at Initial Education
	• 2018-1-HR01-KA201-047499 - Development of Literacy and Language Learning for Disadvantaged Young Learners
	• 2018-1-HR01-KA201-047499 - DEAL (Development of Literacy and Language Learning for Disadvantaged Young Learners)
	• 2016-1-HR01-KA219-022165 - IMAGINE
	• 2016-1-CZ01-KA219-023855 - Together
	• 2017-1-SK01-KA201-035313 - Work for an Inclusive School Heritage (WISH)
	• 2015-1-EL01-KA219-013904 - ARTEMOTION XPRESS IN

	<p>EUROPE</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2017-1-FR01-KA219-037109 - Open your mind through games • 2017-1-IT02-KA201-036699 - The Different Colours of Music
Social inclusion/ community (vulnerability, refugees, disability, accessibility, social mediation)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2021-2-LV01-KA210-SCH-000049347 - Plant-based nutrition and sports • 2017-1-EL01-KA219-036155 - Lifeboats Full of Hopes • 2018-1-CY01-KA229-046925 - Passengers on the Same Bus! No place for discrimination, segregation and inequality • 2020-1-PL01-KA201-081490 - Be a Buddy not a Bully • 2018-1-FR01-KA229-048344 - Dreamers Beyond Borders • 2019-1-SK01-KA229-060793 - Empathy - a way to the human being • 2017-1-HR01-KA219-035417 - A Magical Dream: Animal Assisted Therapy for Disabled Students • 2019-1-NL01-KA201-060346 - Healthy Inclusive Lifestyle through Schools
Inclusive educational technology (digital accessibility, augmented/virtual reality, gamification for diversity)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2020-1-TR01-KA201-093698 - INtegrating Special-needs Individuals into Digi-holistic Education • 2018-1-NL01-KA201-038955 - iExpress Myself II • 2016-1-CY01-KA201-017315 - The Living Book - Augmenting Reading For Life • 2017-1-LT01-KA202-035218 - The Ability Advisor: Improving the Tourism for All Market by VET
Mixed projects (educational and social)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2019-1-SK01-KA229-060793 - Empathy - a way to the human being • 2018-1-FR01-KA229-048344 - Dreamers Beyond Borders • 2018-1-FI01-KA229-047288 - Social Inclusion Handbook (EU Inclusion Approaches) • 2017-1-HR01-KA219-035417 - A Magical Dream: Animal Assisted Therapy for Disabled Students • 2019-1-BG01-KA201-062561 - Learn and Play

Source: Own elaboration (European Commission, 2025)

The analysis of the revised Erasmus+ projects allows us to identify common patterns that can serve as a reference for designing future inclusive initiatives. One of the most reiterated elements is the need for specific teacher training in inclusion, combined with active methodologies and the strategic use of educational technologies.

A relevant group of projects is made up of those aimed at addressing functional diversity and specific educational needs. Many of them have integrated innovative technologies to create more accessible and personalised learning environments, where the use of digital tools and teacher training have been key factors in adequately addressing the heterogeneity of students.

Also noteworthy are those projects focused on the inclusion of immigrant, refugee or cultural minority students. These initiatives have developed strategies based on giving value to linguistic and cultural diversity, mutual recognition and the construction of intercultural citizenship from the classroom, promoting more open and respectful school environments.

Likewise, projects focused on teacher training and methodological innovation are of special importance. These initiatives have worked on the incorporation of emerging technologies, the development of inclusive methodologies and the promotion of healthy lifestyles as components of equity. There are also projects that have linked inclusion with the development of emotional intelligence, highlighting school mediation, empathy and emotional management as axes to improve coexistence and strengthen the sense of belonging.

With regard to the products generated, it is significant that many of them transcend the specific context of the schools involved and offer transferable and useful tools for the education system as a whole. Among the most relevant results are methodological manuals and guides, school mediation protocols, banks of didactic activities, continuous training programs for teachers, educational video games, mobile applications, augmented reading platforms and digital resources to address linguistic, cultural and functional diversity. Adapted pedagogical materials, proposals for project-based learning and assessment and monitoring tools for areas such as language, social skills or emotional development have also been developed (Table 3).

Table 3.

Typology of results generated by the projects (M/P: Manuals / Protocols; FD: Teacher Training; RD: Digital Resources; M/D: SEN Materials/Diversity); PBL: Project-Based Learning)

Project (Ref.)	M/P	FD	RD	M/A	ABP
2021-1-IT02-KA220-SCH-000032841	✓	✓	-	✓	-
2021-2-LV01-KA210-SCH-000049347	-	-	✓	✓	-
2020-1-EL01-KA201-078810	✓	✓	-	✓	-
2020-1-DE03-KA229-077397	✓	-	✓	✓	-
2019-1-EL01-KA229-062543	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
2019-1-SK01-KA229-060793	✓	-	✓	✓	✓
2019-1-NL01-KA201-060346	✓	✓	✓	-	-
2020-1-TR01-KA201-093698	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
2020-1-LV01-KA201-077496	✓	✓	✓	-	✓

2018-1-NL01-KA201-038955	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
2018-1-FI01-KA229-047288	✓	✓	-	-	-
2020-1-PL01-KA201-081490	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
2019-1-BG01-KA201-062561	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
2017-1-BG01-KA201-036295	✓	✓	✓	-	-
2018-1-FR01-KA229-048344	✓	-	✓	✓	-
2017-1-SK01-KA201-035313	✓	✓	✓	-	✓
2017-1-FR01-KA219-037109	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
2017-1-EL01-KA219-036155	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
2017-1-LV01-KA219-035422	✓	-	✓	-	-
2018-1-CY01-KA229-046925	✓	✓	✓	-	-
2015-1-EL01-KA219-013904	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
2018-1-EL01-KA229-047808	✓	✓	✓	-	✓
2018-1-HR01-KA201-047499	✓	✓	✓	-	-
2017-1-SE01-KA219-034589	✓	✓	✓	-	-
2016-1-CY01-KA201-017315	✓	✓	✓	-	-
2017-1-HR01-KA219-035417	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
2017-1-LT01-KA202-035218	✓	✓	✓	-	-
2017-1-IT02-KA201-036699	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
2018-1-BE02-KA101-046687	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
2016-1-HR01-KA219-022165	✓	✓	✓	✓	-
2016-1-CZ01-KA219-023855	✓	✓	✓	✓	-

Source: Own elaboration (European Commission, 2025)

These products not only offer practical and accessible solutions to the challenges of diversity in the classroom, but are also highly transferable and adaptable to different educational levels and national contexts, facilitating their integration into institutional improvement plans, school educational projects and teacher training programmes.

The contribution of these results to the educational community is twofold. On the one hand, they enrich the pedagogical repertoire of teachers and management teams, favouring inclusive evidence-based practices. On the other hand, they strengthen key competencies in students, such as intercultural communication, critical thinking, digital literacy and social commitment, thus promoting more democratic, resilient school environments that are open to collaborative learning and diversity.

Together, these projects reflect the wealth of approaches and strategies promoted through the Erasmus+ programme, confirming that effective inclusion requires comprehensive interventions that combine pedagogical innovation, attention to diversity, accessible technology and work on social and emotional competences.

In this way, the revised projects exemplify Erasmus+ commitment to innovation and educational inclusion, offering transferable models that can be implemented at different levels and contexts of the education system.

5. Discussion and conclusions

Inclusive education brings substantial benefits to both students and school communities as a whole. Various studies indicate that schools that adopt inclusive approaches achieve improvements in overall academic performance, since adaptive methodologies benefit all students, not just those with specific needs (UNESCO, 2021, 2024). In addition, inclusion prepares students to function in a diverse work environment, strengthening key competencies such as empathy, critical thinking, and adaptability.

5.1. Discussion

Building inclusive education systems requires the coordinated commitment of all educational actors. Schools must lead this transformation by incorporating UDL (Alba Pastor, 2019), while teachers, according to Article 91 of the LOE (Ley Orgánica 2/2006, 2006), must adapt its teaching to the characteristics of the students, counting on continuous training and institutional support. The LOMLOE (Ley Orgánica 3/2020, 2020), in addition, reinforces the flexible organisation of schools and consolidates measures such as diversity care plans and support programmes, establishing inclusion as a fundamental principle of educational quality and equity.

For its part, the educational inspectorate, as stated in article 151 of the LOE, plays a key role in providing technical support, ensuring the effective application of these measures, advising on the implementation of good practices and ensuring equity in the processes.

Their work is crucial to promote inclusive environments from a vision that is not only normative, but also pedagogical and collaborative.

Erasmus+ projects are an example of the transformative potential of international collaboration in education. They have shown that it is possible to develop replicable intervention models that integrate institutional leadership, transnational cooperation, and inclusive approaches. Teacher training in technologies such as AI, AR or VR has shown its usefulness in improving accessibility and motivation for the most vulnerable students. In addition, many of these initiatives promote the universal design of materials, the ethical use of technology and the application of Big Data to personalize educational supports and guide public policies more effectively.

However, these projects are implemented in specific contexts and institutions, and their impact remains limited in the face of the structural challenges that persist in the classroom. The shortage of specialized personnel, the overload of teachers in the face of the growing diversity of the student body and the difficulties of coordination with families represent real obstacles that hinder full educational inclusion. In many centres, especially in vulnerable areas, gaps in access to technology limit the development of adapted practices (Fundación Telefónica, 2022b, 2022a; OECD, 2023). Added to this is the lack of sustained investment in accessible infrastructures and specific training programmes, making it difficult to consolidate an inclusive model on a large scale.

In the face of these challenges, in addition to replicating the good practices collected in Erasmus+ projects, it is essential to integrate recommendations such as those in the TALIS report (OECD, 2019, 2020), including the strengthening of teacher training, the promotion of research in inclusive technologies, the evaluation of educational impact through longitudinal studies and the construction of solid alliances between educational centres, administrations and social agents. These lines of action, aligned with the European frameworks (European Commission, 2022; UNESCO, 2023, 2024), allow us to move towards fairer, more inclusive and effective systems.

Finally, collaboration between schools, teachers, inspectorates and families continues to be the driving force behind real inclusion. With a collective effort continued over time, based on equity, accessibility and participation, it is possible to achieve environments where no student is left behind.

5.1. Conclusions

Inclusive education is, in addition to being a right recognised by international organisations such as the UN and UNESCO, an essential way to improve the quality and equity of education systems. Ensuring that all students can learn under conditions of equality does not depend only on access to the classroom, but also on the ability of the system to adapt to the real diversity of its students. This involves changing practices, structures and attitudes, and that is where pedagogical and technological innovation can play a decisive role.

The analysis of the Erasmus+ projects included in this work shows that, when inclusion and innovation are integrated in a coherent way, the results are positive: more accessible, participatory and effective learning environments are generated. Many of these initiatives have developed adapted teaching materials, methodological guides, digital resources and organisational strategies that can be used by other centres. What is relevant is that these are not isolated solutions, but models that can be replicated and adjusted to different educational contexts.

Despite the value of the initiatives promoted by these projects, their scope is often limited by the particular conditions of each context. Thus, structural challenges persist that make it difficult to generalize, such as the scarcity of human and training resources, the complexity of school dynamics and the need to strengthen collaboration with families. Factors such as the digital divide and the lack of sustained investment also play a role, which prevent the consolidation of profound changes. Overcoming these obstacles requires a systemic vision, institutional commitment and a firm commitment to action frameworks that transform not only practices, but also the conditions in which they are developed.

For this reason, it is essential that all measures are accompanied by joint work between schools, teachers, educational inspectorate, administrations and families. It is also key to rigorously assess what works in practice, so that policies and resources can be adjusted to real needs. Educational research and well-used data can be a very useful tool to move in that direction.

Finally, the Erasmus+ projects analysed not only offer local solutions, but also generate collective knowledge that can guide the development of more inclusive, effective education policies adapted to contemporary challenges. Moving towards a truly inclusive school requires assuming diversity as an opportunity and shared responsibility.

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